

Reactivity of some di- and triphenyltin(IV) hydroxamates with ligands containing labile protons

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The reactivity of di- and triphenyltin(IV) hydroxamate complexes of composition $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl_{2-n}(XBHA)_n$ and $(C_6H_5)_3Sn(XBHA)$ ($n = 1$ and 2 ; $X = p\text{-OMe}, o\text{-Cl}, p\text{-NO}_2$; BHA = anion of $XArCONHOK$) with ligands containing labile protons such as acetylacetone (acacH), dibenzoylmethane (dbmH), salicylaldehyde (salH) and *o*-chlorophenol and thiophenol has been studied to investigate the preferential attack on Sn-C, Sn-Cl or Sn-O bond. The title complexes do not react with the chelating ligands. However, the reactions of $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl(XBHA)$ with sodium salt of the chelating ligands NaL (L = acac, dbm and sal) readily proceed to yield the mixed ligand complexes of composition $(C_6H_5)_2Sn(XBHA).L$, while the treatment of $(C_6H_5)_2Sn(XBHA)_2$ and $(C_6H_5)_3Sn(XBHA)$ with phenols results in the complete displacement of the hydroxamate group with the phenolate ion.

Compared to a great increase of knowledge on the synthesis, structural and bonding aspects of metal hydroxamates¹, very little effort has been made to investigate the reactivity of these complexes particularly with ligands containing labile protons. The present communication reports the reactions of some di- and triphenyltin(IV) hydroxamates with some selective ligands containing labile protons.

Results and Discussion

The direct reaction of $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl(XBHA)$ with the chelating ligands acacH, dbmH and salH neither led to an evolution of HCl gas nor yielded any compound of definite composition. However, the reactions with the sodium derivatives of the chelating ligands (NaL) allowed the removal of chlorine from them in the form of NaCl,

where, L = acac, dbm and sal.

The elemental analyses of the complexes (Table 1) agreed well with the proposed stoichiometry. The complexes are fine crystalline solids and are fairly soluble in common organic solvents. The low molar conductance values show their non-electrolytic nature. The molecular weights of the complexes (by cryoscopic method) correspond with the formula weight indicating their monomeric nature.

The ir spectra of the mixed ligand complexes revealed the complete absence of bands at $\sim 350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ attributed to the ν_{Sn-Cl} mode in the parent hydroxamates². The bands due to ν_{N-H} and ν_{C-N} modes of the hydroxamate ion shifted to the higher frequency side compared to those in parent

Table 1 Analytical and physical data of the compounds*

Compd (Formula)	Yield (M p °C)	Sn% Found (Calcd)	Λ_M $\Omega^{-1}\text{ cm}^2\text{ mol}^{-1}$
$(C_6H_5)_2Sn(p\text{-OMeBHA})\text{ acac}$ ($SnC_{25}H_{25}NO_5$)	72 (210)	22.2 (22.0)	-
$(C_6H_5)_2Sn(p\text{-OMeBHA})\text{ dbm}$ ($SnC_{35}H_{29}NO_5$)	76 (218)	17.5 (17.9)	1.2
$(C_6H_5)_2Sn(o\text{-Cl-}p\text{-NO}_2\text{BHA})\text{ sal}$ ($SnC_{26}H_{19}ClNO_4$)	68	22.4 (22.5)	-
$(C_6H_5)_2Sn(o\text{-Cl-}p\text{-NO}_2\text{BHA})\text{ acac}$ ($SnC_{24}H_{21}ClN_2O_6$)	63	22.09 (22.5)	1.7
$(C_6H_5)_2Sn(o\text{-Cl-}p\text{-NO}_2\text{BHA})\text{ dbm}$ ($SnC_{34}H_{25}ClN_2O_6$)	67 (176)	16.4 (16.6)	2.2

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H and Cl (where applicable) analyses.

complexes, probably owing to the introduction of chelating ligands. However, the characteristic vibrations of the coordinated hydroxamate and secondary ligands at $1600\text{--}1300\text{ cm}^{-1}$, which generally show significant changes on complexation, could not be distinguished in the complexes because of the mixing or overlapping of C=C and C=O stretching bands. The bands observed at ~ 340 and 560 cm^{-1} have been attributed to ν_{Sn-C} and ν_{Sn-O} modes respectively³. Coordination from carbonyl oxygen of the secondary ligands has been inferred from the significant shift of the band due to $\nu_{C=O}$. Thus an octahedral environment around tin may tentatively be proposed.

Reactions of $(C_6H_5)_2Sn(XBHA)_2$ and $(C_6H_5)_3Sn(XBHA)$ with phenols: Compared to the well known reactions⁴ of isopropoxides of aluminium(III), titanium(IV) and

zirconium(IV) with benzo- and phenylacetohydroxamic acids, the reactions of metal hydroxamates with phenols are not known. This prompted us to undertake the reactions of the parent complexes with these ligands. The reaction of $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl(XBHA)$ with phenols gave the solids which could not be identified for their stoichiometric composition, while $(C_6H_5)_2Sn(XBHA)_2$ and $(C_6H_5)_3Sn(XBHA)$ reacted with thiophenol and *o*-chlorophenol according to the reaction scheme,

where, $Y = OC_6H_4Cl-o$ or SC_6H_5 and when $x = 3, y = 1$; $x = 2, y = 2$

wherein thiophenoxy and *o*-chlorophenoxy ligands replaced the coordinated hydroxamate ligands from the parent complexes.

The elemental analysis data and m.ps. of the resulting solids correspond to the formation of organotin(IV) thiophenoxide and *o*-chlorophenoxides (Table 2). A negative $FeCl_3$ test also supports their formation. The disappearance of the characteristic bands of hydroxamate ligand due to $\nu_{C=O}$, ν_{C-N} , ν_{N-O} and ν_{N-H} in the complexes further substantiates the removal of hydroxamate ion from the parent complexes and concomitant incorporation of phenoxy group is suggested.

Table 2. Analytical and ir spectral (cm^{-1}) data of the compounds*

Compd.	M.p. °C	Analysis % :		ν_{max} (cm^{-1})
		Found/(Calcd.)		
		Sn	Cl	
$(C_6H_5)_2Sn(SC_6H_5)_2$	67	24.3 (24.1)	-	1122 (C=S), 428 (Sn-S)
$(C_6H_5)_2Sn(o-ClC_6H_4O)_2$	>250	22.2 (22.4)	13.2 (13.4)	1172 (C=O), 510 (Sn-O)
$(C_6H_5)_3Sn(SC_6H_5)$	104	26.0 (25.8)	-	1118 (C=S), 425 (Sn-S)
$(C_6H_5)_3Sn(o-ClC_6H_4O)$	-	24.6 (24.8)	7.2 (7.4)	1170 (C=O), 495 (Sn-O)

The Mössbauer parameters for some of the complexes, viz. $(C_6H_5)_2Sn(XBHA)_2.L$ [$XBHA = p-OMeC_6H_4CONHO^-$ and $L = acac$ and dbm] and $(C_6H_5)_2Sn(OC_6H_4Cl-o)_2$ and $(C_6H_5)_3Sn(OC_6H_4Cl-o)$ have shown the isomer shift values (δ) to lie in the range $0.76-0.87$ mm S^{-1} and $0.78-1.03$ mm S^{-1} , known for diphenyltin(IV) and triphenyltin(IV) complexes respectively. The slight reduction in the isomer shift may be attributed to the interaction between tin and ketonic/phenolic oxygens bonded to the metal atom. The closeness of isomer shift values indicates that the *s*-electron density

about the nucleus is similar in these complexes. The appearance of a relatively large resolvable ΔE_Q in the ranges $1.7-1.95$ and $1.8-2.0$ mm S^{-1} for the di- and triphenyltin(IV) complexes respectively, may be due to distortion arising mainly due to imbalance of *p*-electrons in the lone-pair orbital of the ligand around tin. The ratio $Qs/IS = p$, in the complexes are consistent with coordination number six and four.

To conclude, the results of the reactivity of organotin(IV) hydroxamates in the presence of chelating ligands and phenols indicate the stability of the Sn-C bond. Reactions of $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl(XBHA)$ with sodium derivatives of chelating ligands show the breaking of Sn-Cl bond while the reactions of bare chloro di- and triphenyltin(IV) complexes with phenols concede the replacement of coordinated hydroxamate ion by phenoxide ion.

Experimental

$(C_6H_5)_2SnCl_2$ (Aldrich) and $(C_6H_5)_3SnCl$ (Fluka) were used as such. The purity of the materials was however checked by their sharp m.ps. and chlorine analysis. *p*-Methoxybenzohydroxamic acid and *o*-chloro-*p*-nitrobenzohydroxamic acids were prepared by the reported methods⁵. The sodium derivatives of acetylacetone, dibenzoylmethane and salicylaldehyde were prepared by standard methods⁶.

Complexes of compositions $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl_{2-n}(XBHA)_n$ and $(C_6H_5)_3Sn(XBHA)$ were prepared by mixing together the THF solution of $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl_2$ and $(C_6H_5)_3SnCl$ with stoichiometric amounts of potassium *p*-methoxy- and *o*-chloro-*p*-nitrobenzohydroxamates dissolved in methanol and heating under reflux. KCl formed during the reaction was removed by filtration and the filtrate was concentrated by distilling off the solvents. The concentrated solution gave the products as fine solids, which were crystallized from methanol.

Reactions of $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl(XBHA)$ with acacNa, dbmNa and salNa : The methanolic solution of $(C_6H_5)_2SnCl(XBHA)$ was treated with the solution of acacNa, dbmNa or salNa in the same solvent and refluxed for 6-8 h. The resulting white solid was filtered. The filtrate was concentrated and set aside. The solid complexes obtained were washed with petroleum ether and crystallized from methanol.

*Reactions of $(C_6H_5)_2Sn(XBHA)_2$ and $(C_6H_5)_3Sn(XBHA)$ with thiophenol (HSC_6H_5) and *o*-chlorophenol (HOC_6H_4Cl-o)* : A suspension of $(C_6H_5)_2Sn(XBHA)_2$ and $(C_6H_5)_3Sn(XBHA)$ in dry benzene was treated with an excess of thiophenol and *o*-chlorophenol, and the mixture was refluxed. The fine solids so obtained were washed with

petroleum ether and dried under reduced pressure. The excess phenol was then removed by distillation. The quantitative amounts of fine crystals of the hydroxamic acids appeared and their m.ps. corresponded with those of reported ones.

The tin was determined as SnO₂. Chlorine was determined by Volhard's method. Conductivity (10⁻³ M solution of the complexes in nitrobenzene) was measured on an Elico CM-82T conductivity bridge. Ir spectra (KBr/CsI) were recorded on a Beckman IR-4250 spectrophotometer. Mössbauer spectra were obtained using a constant acceleration microprocessor spectrometer (Cryophysics) with samples cooled by liquid nitrogen (80 K) and the source was 15 mCiCa^{119m}SnO₃ at room temperature.

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